

Condition of Silver Chloride and other sparingly soluble Substances in Gelatine.

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There is considerable difference of opinion amongst colloid chemists regarding the condition of substances like silver chloride, silver bromide, lead iodide, mercuric iodide, and other sparingly soluble substances when formed in presence of gels like gelatine, agar-agar, starch etc. Many people seem to believe that these sparingly soluble substances exist in gels in the supersaturated condition. Thus Freundlich ("Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," English Translation, p. 734) states: "Silver chromate in gelatine is always in supersaturated solution." In previous papers (Chatterji and Dhar, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, **72**, 23; *Kolloid Zeit.*, 1925, **35**, 2, 89; 1926 **40**, 97) we have emphasised and shown experimentally that the above view is incorrect and that these substances exist mainly in the colloidal state. We have proved from electric conductivity measurements of silver chromate in varying concentrations of gelatine that the observed conductivity is much less than the conductivity calculated on the assumption that silver chromate exists wholly as ions in gelatine. Moreover diffusion experiments show that silver chromate, lead iodide etc., formed in gelatine or agar have no appreciable velocity of diffusion.

From our experiments on the electric conductivity of saturated and supersaturated solutions of substances like calcium chloride, sodium acetate etc., we find that there is no break in the conductivity curve when we pass from the saturated to the supersaturated solution. In other words, there is no marked difference in the physical properties of saturated and supersaturated solutions of electrolytes. Several years ago W. Ostwald ("Solutions" p. 59, 1891) stated: "That the electrical conductivity suffers no irregular change when the point of saturation is passed has been shown by C. Heim." Consequently it is difficult to understand how substances like silver chloride, silver chromate etc., can remain in the supersaturated condition in gelatine, because these substances when formed in gelatine do not show much electric conductivity.

The objection may be raised that in presence of the viscous medium gelatine or agar-agar, the electric conductivity will be

greatly decreased due to the viscosity of the medium ; but Arrhenius proved long ago that electric conductivity of substances like HCl, HNO₃, etc., when set in gelatine is practically the same as in aqueous solution of the same concentration under otherwise identical conditions.

In order to throw further light on the condition of sparingly soluble substances in gels we have carefully determined the electric conductivity of silver chloride formed in gelatine.

Experiments were undertaken to find out the conductivity of different amounts of silver chloride in gelatine of varying strengths at 35°.

Kahlbaum "Golddruck" gelatine was further purified by precipitating it from an aqueous solution by the addition of absolute alcohol. It was then dried at 85° and dissolved in conductivity water. This solution of gelatine was further freed from electrolytes by dialysis for a week until it showed no turbidity with silver nitrate.

The conductivity of the gelatine solution increased slightly with time on keeping and hence after each set of experiments the solution was dialysed for a day, and used for subsequent experiments after a fresh determination of the electric conductivity.

As silver chloride was obtained by the addition of equivalent quantities of silver nitrate and potassium chloride, an equivalent amount of potassium nitrate was also produced. In order to ascertain the conductivity of silver chloride alone, the conductivity of an equivalent concentration of potassium nitrate in gelatine was determined under identical conditions.

A typical result of the conductivity experiments is shown in Table 1.

TABLE I.

Concentration of gelatine	1.087	grm. in 100 c.c.
Concentration of silver nitrate, potassium chloride etc.	N/800	
Conductivity of water at 35°	2.5×10^{-6}	mhos.
Conductivity of gelatine	0.279×10^{-3}	„
Conductivity of gelatine and silver nitrate	0.387×10^{-3}	„
Conductivity of gelatine and potassium chloride	0.481×10^{-3}	„
Conductivity of gelatine, silver chloride and potassium nitrate	0.4834×10^{-3}	„
Conductivity of gelatine and potassium nitrate	0.4821×10^{-3}	„
Hence observed conductivity of silver chloride			0.0013×10^{-3}	„

Exactly similar results were obtained with other concentrations of silver chloride and gelatine and the results obtained are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II.

Concentration of silver chloride.	Concentration of gelatine.	Conductivity observed. (mbos).	Conductivity as calculated from the experiments assuming AgCl to be in the ionic condition (Mhos).	Conductivity observed expressed as percentage of calculated conductivity.
N/800	1.1%	0.0013×10^{-3}	0.1068×10^{-3}	0.84
N/400	„	0.0052×10^{-3}	0.2839×10^{-3}	1.8
N/320	„	0.0187×10^{-3}	0.4986×10^{-3}	3.9
N/160	„	-0.042×10^{-3}	0.8026×10^{-3}	...
N/106.6	„	-0.417×10^{-3}	1.2965×10^{-3}	...
N/800	0.64%	0.0027×10^{-3}	0.1477×10^{-3}	1.1
N/160	3.45%	-0.0140×10^{-3}	0.5600×10^{-3}	...
N/80	„	-0.0374×10^{-3}	1.320×10^{-3}	...
N/53.3	„	-0.0650×10^{-3}	2.116×10^{-3}	...
N/160	3.15%	-0.0850×10^{-3}	0.384×10^{-3}	...
N/106.6	„	-0.085×10^{-3}	0.745×10^{-3}	...

From the conductivity measurements given in Table I, the conductivity of silver chloride as determined by experiments can be ascertained by simply subtracting the conductivity of potassium nitrate from that of the mixture of silver chloride and potassium nitrate. If it is supposed that silver chloride remains in the ionic condition and not in the colloidal state, then its conductivity should be equal to the sum of the conductivities of silver nitrate and potassium chloride less the conductivity of potassium nitrate. Table II contains the results calculated on the basis of the above considerations.

From Table II it will be evident that if silver chloride were present in the ionic condition, the conductivity of this substance would have been much greater than the values actually obtained. As a matter of fact in the majority of the cases investigated the minus sign in the column of observed conductivity indicates that the conductivity of a mixture of silver chloride and potassium nitrate is less than the conductivity of potassium nitrate alone. As the

amount of silver chloride present in these experiments is sufficiently large, it seems that silver chloride in the course of its formation adsorbs some potassium nitrate, thereby lowering its effective concentration. Thus from our experimental results it will be seen that when the concentration of silver chloride is varied from N/160 to N/53.3 we always get appreciable adsorption of potassium nitrate by silver chloride causing negative value in the observed conductivity. On the other hand, when more dilute solutions of silver nitrate are used and when the concentration of AgCl varies from N/800 to N/266.6, the observed conductivity is positive, because the amount of adsorption of potassium nitrate is less than in those experiments where more concentrated solutions of silver nitrate were used.

Hence the foregoing experimental results lead us to the conclusion that silver chloride formed in gelatine by the reaction of silver nitrate and potassium chloride exists in the colloidal state.

In order to corroborate our experiments with silver chromate in gelatine published in a previous paper we have carried on numerous experiments with gelatine of known conductivity in which silver chromate was allowed to form by the interaction of potassium chromate and silver nitrate and the following results were obtained.

TABLE III.

	Concentration of silver chromate.	Concentration of gelatine.	Conductivity observed (mbos.)	Conductivity calculated on the assumption that Ag_2CrO_4 is in the ionic condition (mbos.)	Observed conductivity expressed as percentage of calc. conductivity.	Conductivity of gelatine (mbos.)
1	N/100	3%	0.1425×10^{-3}	0.8010×10^{-3}	17.7%	0.4786×10^{-3}
2	N/500	3%	0.1310×10^{-3}	0.3022×10^{-3}	43.2%	0.5108×10^{-3}
3	N/120	3.25%	0.1833×10^{-3}	0.5772×10^{-3}	31.7%	0.3800×10^{-3}
4	N/700	3.25%	0.0156×10^{-3}	0.0532×10^{-3}	29.3%	0.4630×10^{-3}
5	N/280	2.75%	0.2455×10^{-3}	0.7453×10^{-3}	32.8%	0.6022×10^{-3}
6	N/400	2.6%	0.1347×10^{-3}	0.2809×10^{-3}	47.9%	0.6716×10^{-3}
7	N/320	2.6%	0.0153×10^{-3}	0.1520×10^{-3}	10.1%	1.2766×10^{-3} (undialysed).
8	N/106.8	2.6%	0.156×10^{-3}	0.8010×10^{-3}	19.4%	1.790×10^{-3} (undialysed).
9	N/320	8.15%	0.0095×10^{-3}	0.1805×10^{-3}	5.2%	1.563×10^{-3}
10	N/160	8.15%	0.1245×10^{-3}	0.6485×10^{-3}	19.0%	1.585×10^{-3}
	The conductivity of the water used = 2.5×10^{-6} mbos. at 85°					

In Table XIV of their paper Bolam and Mackenzie (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 67, 160) point out that "the amount of silver other than ion is directly proportional to the gelatine concentration." The following table which is taken from their paper will illustrate their conclusion.

TABLE IV.

Ag-Ag° Normality × 10 ⁵	Gelatine per cent.	$\frac{\text{Ag-Ag}^\circ}{\text{Gelatine concentration}}$
(333-108)	3.0	$\frac{333-108}{3} = 75 \times 10^{-5}$
(236-106)	1.59	$\frac{236-106}{1.59} = 82 \times 10^{-5}$
(162-108)	0.70	$\frac{162-103}{0.70} = 77 \times 10^{-5}$

They obtained the above table from the results recorded in Table II. of their paper where only the minimum quantity of gelatine necessary to prevent precipitation was present. But if we calculate the relationship between the amount of silver other than ion and the gelatine concentration from the results recorded by Bolam and Mackenzie in Table V of their paper where the concentrations of gelatine as well as of silver chromate were widely varied we get results which are given in the following table. The mean value obtained from the *E. M. F.* data in the final reading has been taken to indicate the amount of silver present as ion.

TABLE V.

Ag-Ag° Normality × 10 ⁵	Gelatine per cent.	$\frac{\text{Ag-Ag}^\circ}{\text{Gelatine concentration}}$
(333-108.4)	3.0	74.86×10^{-5}
(250-68)	3.0	68.67×10^{-5}
(125-14.5)	3.0	37.17×10^{-5}
(236-106.8)	1.59	81.26×10^{-5}
(118-35.9)	1.59	51.63×10^{-5}
(324-66)	0.70	368.57×10^{-5}
(162-108)	0.70	77.14×10^{-5}
(338-35.7)	6.00	49.66×10^{-5}
(333-59.7)	4.50	60.73×10^{-5}
(236-50.3)	3.17	58.58×10^{-5}
(236-83.7)	2.11	72.18×10^{-5}
(236-134.2)	1.06	96.03×10^{-5}
(162-41)	2.1	57.61×10^{-5}
(162-67.2)	1.4	67.71×10^{-5}
(162-117.7)	0.35	126.57×10^{-5}

From the above table it will be at once evident that there exists no definite relation between the amount of silver that is present other than in the ionic condition and the quantity of gelatine in the solution.

Moreover, it is apparent from the results obtained by Bolam and Mackenzie that the quantity of silver present as ion calculated from the *E.M.F.* data is much less than the total amount of silver present. The following table which is obtained from the results of Bolam and Mackenzie given in their Table V shows the relation between the total amount of silver and the quantity present as ion.

TABLE VI.

Concentration of gelatine in per cent.	Total amount of silver. Normality $\times 10^5$	Amount of silver as ions. Normality $\times 10^5$	Percentage of silver present as ions.
3	333	108.4	32.6
3	250	68.0	27.2
3	125	14.5	11.6
1.59	236	106.8	45.2
1.59	118	35.9	30.4
0.70	324	66.0	20.4
0.70	162	108.0	66.6
6.0	333	35.7	10.7
4.5	333	59.7	17.9
3.0	333	108.4	32.6
1.5	333	104.8	31.5
1.0	333	74.6	22.4
3.17	236	50.3	21.3
2.11	236	88.7	35.3
1.59	236	106.2	45.0
1.06	236	134.2	56.8
1.06	236	82.6	33.6
1.06	236	67.8	28.7
2.10	162	41.0	25.3
1.4	182	67.2	41.4
0.70	162	108.2	66.6
0.85	162	117.7	72.6
0.35	162	65.2	40.2

From the above table it will be clear that the amount of silver present as ion is in the majority of cases less than 40% of the total silver, or in other words, nearly two thirds of the silver exists in a form other than ionic.

We are of the opinion that the two thirds of the silver, which does not exist in the ionic condition, remain in the colloidal state. Hence the measurements of Bolam and Mackenzie are in support of our views that the sparingly soluble substance formed in presence of gelatine exists as a colloid. Moreover it should be emphasised that the hydrogen ions present in gelatine exert a solvent action on the silver chromate formed, because silver chromate dissolves in acids and hence more free silver ions are detected in the solution due to the existence of hydrogen ions in gelatine. In the case of silver chloride the hydrogen ions present in gelatine cannot dissolve silver chloride and hence the amount of free silver ions present with silver chloride is much less than the amount found in the case of silver chromate.

Summary and Conclusion.

(1) Measurements of electrical conductivity of silver chloride of different concentrations in gelatine prove that the observed conductivity is much less than the conductivity calculated on the assumption that silver chloride exists wholly as ions in gelatine.

Exactly similar results have been obtained with silver chromate in gelatine.

(2) From the experimental results of Bolam and Mackenzie with silver chromate in gelatine it can be concluded that there exists no definite relationship between the amount of silver present in the non-ionic condition and the quantity of gelatine present. Their experiments on *E.M.F.* measurements shew that the amount of silver present in the ionic condition in silver chromate in gelatine is approximately 40 per cent.

(3) In the case of silver chloride the hydrogen ions present in gelatine cannot dissolve silver chloride and hence the amount of free silver ions present with silver chloride is much less than in the case of silver chromate in gelatine.

(4) Our experimental results show that silver chloride, silver chromate etc., formed in gelatine exist mainly in the colloidal state.

